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WHAT INFLUENCES DONOR BEHAVIOR DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC? A PREDICTIVE CROSS-SECTIONAL ANALYSIS IN THE PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

The donor behavior has increased to mitigate the economic impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic especially among those who have lost their jobs and source of income during this time (Nicola et al., 2020). In this predictive cross-sectional analysis, the study aims to investigate the influence of demographics (sex, age, socioeconomic status), empathy, altruism, and social media on donor behavior among Filipino donors in the National Capital Region in the Philippines, guided by Andreoni's (1989) Theory of Warm Glow. The researchers used three affective survey-type instruments in gathering data, namely Interpersonal Reactivity Index (IRI) for empathy, The Self-Report Altruism Scale (SRA) for altruism, and the Surtida & Hernandez Donor Behavior Scale (SHDBS) for donor behavior. The researchers used a separate survey questionnaire for demographics. After gathering the data, the researchers analyzed the data using Descriptive Statistics, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), General Regression, and General Linear Models to explain the influence of demographics, altruism, empathy, and social media on donor behavior. The researchers found that demographics, source, altruism, and empathy are not significant predictors of donor behavior in the Philippine context during the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: *altruism, COVID-19, demographics, donor behavior, social media*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 virus has become the cause of many deaths throughout the entire globe since its outburst in 2019 (World Health Organization, 2021). The first known infection of the virus was discovered in Wuhan, China and is transmissible through the spread of droplets (Galbadage et al., 2020) which has caused the implementation of social distancing, self-isolation, and travel restrictions. This has also led to the reduction of workforce and loss of jobs globally (Nicola et al., 2020). Due to the effects of this pandemic, many people have faced financial concerns (Wilson et al., 2020). The present situation has affected many people in the Philippines, especially those who are under the poverty line. These individuals have been finding it difficult to gather necessities such as food, toiletries, etc. Another factor is that a lot of these people lost their sources of income due to quarantine restrictions (Murakami et al., 2021; Kang et al., 2021). This has sparked the initiative of financially abled individuals to host donation drives and community pantries for them to be able to help people during the pandemic (Cleofas, 2021). This movement has influenced many people around the country and has inspired other communities and organizations to start fundraising activities. Although, this is not a sustainable economic support for those who are economically disadvantaged during the pandemic, this has served as a huge help to those in need to survive during the pandemic.

The initiative of helping people in need in times of crisis is called donor behavior. Donor behavior, as defined by Ülkü et al., (2015) is the ability of an individual to donate to other people. It is the willingness of an individual to help other people in times of crisis. This could be influenced by different factors that could affect the increase or decrease of the willingness to donate. The past literature has argued that factors including demographics – age, sex, and socioeconomic status – can influence one's donor behavior. Past studies have argued that donation intention and perception could vary depending on a donor's demographic (Maftai, 2019; Noor et al., 2015).

Donor behavior is often associated with an individual's empathy and altruism. As defined by De Waal, (2008) altruism refers to a specific form of motivation to benefit another individual. Andreoni et al., (2015) suggested that altruism in an individual could positively influence the donation intention of a donor. Rodrigues et al., (2021) suggested that altruism could also be the likeliness of the individual to donate depending on the level of empathy that the donor has.

Altruism is often associated with empathy and sometimes could not be differentiated, although there is a fine line between these variables wherein altruism is a manifestation of empathy. Empathy is the process where an individual puts themselves in the situation of another to fully understand or to relate to the other person. It could be motivated by external factors such as advertising messages that could motivate the donation intent (Verhaert & Van den Poel, 2011). Lili et al., (2018) states that empathy and perceived credibility of individuals is a powerful and additive role when it comes to their intention to donate money.

Furthermore, it was also observed that donation behavior could be influenced by environmental factors including social media, peers, and other mediums of information. Presence of social media platforms could highly affect the donation intention among individuals (Bin-Nashwan & Al-Daihani, 2020). It was observed that social media advertisements of donation activities influence donation behavior among individuals who tend to spend an ample amount of time on social media. However, not all donors are active in using social media. In the study of Neumayr & Handy, (2019) it was found that church goers tend to participate in donation activities when it is affiliated with their religious organization. Other mediums could be newspapers and newsletters where the donation activity could be posted (Zagefka & James, 2015).

However, previous literature focused more on Western countries as a setting for charitable donations. Little information regarding the Asian context was discussed. Charitable donations during the COVID-19 pandemic also lack in terms of literature. Present literature focused on the discussion of demographics such as age, gender, and socioeconomic status as it influences donor behavior (van Rijn et al., 2019; Varnum et al., 2015; Wiepking & James, 2013; Willer et al., 2015) and how each demographic differs on how it influences donor behavior (Beadle et al., 2013; Freeman et al., 2009; Human & Terblanche, 2012; Maftai, 2019; Noor et al., 2015; Rueckert et al., 2011; Schlegelmilch et al., 1997; Shelley & Jay Polonsky, 2002; Snipes et al., 2010; van Diepen et al., 2009; van Rijn et al., 2019; Varnum et al., 2015; Wiepking & James, 2013; Willer et al., 2015) but were all set in Western countries. Furthermore, there are limited studies that focus on how environmental factors influences the donor behavior of an individual in a pandemic (Bin-Nashwan & Al-Daihani, 2020; Neumayr & Handy, 2019; Wiepking, 2010; Zagefka & James, 2015).

The researchers chose to study donor behavior in the Philippine context since they have observed that Filipino donors have been actively donating during the pandemic. The researchers wanted to explain how the presented variables (demographics, altruism, empathy, and environmental factors) could possibly influence the donation intention in a Filipino donor. The researchers specifically chose to study donation intention among donors residing in the National Capital Region since this sector has been placed in multiple lockdowns which led to loss of jobs and sources of income for many residents.

The present study aims to explain how the social independent variables of empathy, altruism, along with demographics and environmental factors could influence the donor behavior among Filipinos during this time of the pandemic. Particularly, the researchers are interested to find out how selected demographics, empathy, altruism, and environmental factors, influence donor behavior among individuals, how these factors influence donor behavior when combined, and how these factors differ when grouped according to demographics. The researchers also aim to study these variables under the Philippine context during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The research aims to know if these variables are evident among Filipino donors during the pandemic. Additionally, it aims to be a source of insight on human behavior in times of crisis and contribute to the literature regarding donor behavior, specifically in the Philippine context. Using the Theory of Warm Glow (Andreoni, 1989) as a guide, the researchers hypothesize that there are differences in donor behavior as influenced by

empathy, altruism, and environmental factors in the Philippine context during the COVID-19 pandemic. The researchers also hypothesize that there are demographic differences on donor behavior among Filipino donors.

Research Questions

This study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the Filipino donor-participants during the COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippine context?
2. Do demographics (sex, age, and socioeconomic status) empathy, altruism, and environmental factors explain donor behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippine context?
3. Are there significant differences in empathy, altruism, and donor behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic when grouped according to demographics and environmental factors?

METHODOLOGY

The researchers used a non-experimental cross-sectional predictive research design as defined by Johnson (2001). The researchers chose this type of research design because the researchers predicted the influence of their proposed independent variables towards the dependent variable. In line with this, the purpose of a cross-sectional predictive is to foretell what will happen or how it influences the dependent variable in one's concept. In predicting the influences of independent variables towards dependent variables, the researchers gathered the data in a single point of time or in present time/situation.

This study took place in the Philippines, specifically in the National Capital Region, during the COVID-19 pandemic. The National Capital Region has faced multiple lockdowns and community quarantines due to the surge of COVID related cases and involves Filipino donors who have been actively donating during the pandemic. The intended sample size was 400, however the researchers gathered only 348 respondents.

The researchers utilized three quantitative data gathering instruments which includes a form that the participants filled up where they disclosed their age, sex, and their monthly income. They were also asked about the number of times they have donated, type of donation, and their source of donation information. In measuring altruism among participants, the researchers utilized the modified 20-item Self-Report Altruism Scale which is used to measure altruistic behavior among individuals (Rushton et al., 1981). The Self-Report Altruism (SRA) scale utilizes a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (very often). In measuring the empathy of the participants, the researchers used the 28-item modified Interpersonal Reactivity Index (IRI) scale, which is developed and described as a multidimensional approach to individual differences in empathy (Davis, 1980). The Interpersonal Reactivity Index (IRI) scale utilizes a five-point, Likert-type scale ranging from 1 ("does not describe me well") to 5 ("describes me very well"). In measuring the donor behavior, the researchers utilized the Surtida & Hernandez

Donor Behavior Scale (SHDBS), a 30-item scale, which is developed to measure donor behavior among charitable donors (Hernandez & Surtida, 2021). The SHDBS utilizes a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree).

The researchers gathered the data using the snowball sampling technique which was applied to the sample population which are Filipino donors residing in the National Capital Region. The researchers distributed the Google form links to charitable donors during the COVID-19 pandemic, both male and females. The researchers also asked the respondents to share the Google form link to fellow donors who have experienced donating during the pandemic. Participants for this survey were presented with an informed consent which gives them the option to participate and allow the researchers to use the data that were collected from the answers or to decline participation and not allow the use of the data collected.

Gender	Frequency		%
	Absolute	Relative	
Male	201	0.58	58
Female	147	0.42	42
Total	348	1	100

To address the three research questions in this predictive cross-sectional study on the influences of demographics, altruism, and empathy to donor behavior among Filipino donors in the Philippines, the researchers used descriptive statistics for research question 1, analysis of variance and general regression for research question 2, and general linear models for research question 3.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the demographic profile of Filipino donor-participants during the COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippine context?*

After an extensive data gathering utilizing social media platforms and email, the researchers have gathered 387 participants who have participated in the survey. The researchers a normality test which resulted in 348 participants. The researchers have analyzed four categories of the demographic profile among Filipino donor-participants: sex, age, employment status, and socioeconomic status.

Table 3.1.

Gender of Participants

Table 1 shows the number of male and female participants that participated in the study. According to the study of Van Rijn et al. (2019), females have a higher tendency of donating compared to males as females have higher empathy compared to males. In this study, it was found that the number of males who have donated during the pandemic in the National Capitol Region are higher than the number of females.

Table 3.2.*Age classification of respondents*

Age Group Classification	Frequency		%
	Absolute	Relative	
Adolescence	290	0.83	83
Early Adulthood	49	0.14	14
Middle Adulthood	9	0.03	3
Total	348	1	100

Table 2 focuses on the different age groups of the respondents that have participated in the study. The researchers utilized Erikson's Stages of Development (Erikson, 1994), as a basis for the age group classification in this study. The respondents were grouped according to the following classifications: Adolescence (ages 18-22 years old), Early Adulthood (ages 23-39 years old), and Middle Adulthood (ages 40-59 years old). It was found via this analysis that most donor-respondents are Adolescents.

Table 3.3.*Employment status of respondents*

Employment Status	Frequency		%
	Absolute	Relative	
Employed in Private Company	36	0.10	10
Government Employee	3	0.01	1
Self-Employed	19	0.06	6
Student	290	0.83	83
Total	348	1	100

Table 3.3 explains the different employment statuses of the respondents that have participated in the study. It was found that most of the respondent-donors during the pandemic were students residing in the National Capital Region.

Table 3.4.*Socioeconomic status of the respondents*

Socioeconomic Status Classification	Monthly Income	Frequency		%
		Absolute	Relative	
A	At least PHP 157,800	5	0.01	1
B	PHP 118,350 – PHP 157,800	7	0.02	2
C	PHP 78,900 – PHP 118,350	2	0.01	1

D	PHP 31,560 – PHP 78,900	20	0.06	6
E	PHP 15,780 – PHP 31,560	35	0.10	10
F	PHP 7,890 – PHP 15,780	43	0.12	12
G	Less than PHP 7,890	236	0.68	68
Total		348	1	100

The researchers utilized the income table as stated in the Family Income and Expenditure Survey (FIES) (Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), 2018) and the Profile and Determinants of the Middle-Income Class in the Philippines (Ramon et al., 2018). It was found that most of the donors in the National Capital Region belongs in class G who has a monthly income not exceeding P 7,890.00 per month.

Research Question 2: Do demographics (sex, age, and socioeconomic status) empathy, altruism, and environmental factors explain donor behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippine context?

Figure 3.1. Age as a predictor of Donor Behavior

As shown in figure 3.1, donor-respondents who belong to the age group (ages 23-39 years old) have a higher donor behavior compared to other age groups. However, the researchers noted that these groups have an effect size of 0.008774, which means that there are no significant differences between the compared groups.

Figure 3.2. Sex as a predictor of Donor Behavior

This graph shows that males have higher tendencies to donate or has more time do participate in donation activities compared to males during the COVID-19 pandemic. This contradicts the findings of past literature (Van Rijn et al., 2019) that females have higher tendencies of donating compared to males as females would have higher empathy. It is noted that the effect size of this group is 0.000241 meaning that there is no significant difference between the groups.

Figure 3.3. Employment Status as a predictor of Donor Behavior

This graph shows that individuals who are self-employed have higher chances of donating during the pandemic. The effect size of this group is 0.013358 which means that there is no significant difference between the groups.

Figure 3.4. Class as a predictor of Donor Behavior

This graph shows that individuals who belong to class C with a monthly income of PHP 78,900 – PHP 118,350 (based on Family Income and Expenditure Survey (FIES) (Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), 2018)) - tends to donate more during the times of COVID-19 pandemic. Statistically, the compared groups have no significant differences. The effect size of this group is 0.028834.

Figure 3.5. Source as a predictor of donor behavior

This graph shows that individuals who have get donation information (place of donation, charity, etc.) have a higher donation behavior compared to those who get their information from other sources. Statistically, there is no significant difference between the groups with a partial ETA of 0.010744.

Table 3.5.*Empathy and Altruism as predictors of Donor Behavior*

Effect	b*	Std.Err. of b*	b	Std.Err. of b	t(345)
Intercept			3.150105	0.210534	14.96244
IRI MEAN	0.028944	0.058067	0.031472	0.063140	0.49845
SRA MEAN	-0.098748	0.058067	-0.068124	0.040059	-1.70059

According to past literature and studies, empathy and altruism are significant predictors of donor behavior among donors. Both variables are often associated with each other and one's altruism can depend on the level of empathy a donor has (Rodrigues et al., 2021). However, the researchers found that these variables are not significant predictors of donor behavior in the Philippine context.

Research Question 3: Are there significant differences on the influences of empathy and altruism on donor behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic when grouped according to the demographics and environmental factors?

Table 3.6.*General linear models' analysis on the differences on the influence on donor behavior of empathy, altruism, demographics, and source*

Effect	SS	Degr. of Freedom	MS	F	p
Intercept	30.09660	1	30.09660	173.5709	0.000000
SRA MEAN	0.57879	1	0.57879	3.3380	0.068604
IRI MEAN	0.06334	1	0.06334	0.3653	0.546004
Age Classification	0.16091	2	0.08045	0.4640	0.629179
Sex	0.03985	1	0.03985	0.2298	0.631981
Employment Status	0.58361	3	0.19454	1.1219	0.340235

Class	1.95576	6	0.32596	1.8799	0.083639
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Table 3.6 shows the significant differences between the effects of altruism, empathy, demographics, and source on donor behavior. The researchers utilized general linear models as the analysis for these variables since the variables are both categorical and continuous. It was found that none of the variables has yielded a significant relationship with donor behavior. None of the variables, when grouped together, significantly affects donor behavior.

It was also found by the researchers that empathy among the donor-respondents doesn't significantly affect their donor behavior even if they are grouped according to demographics and source. However, the results with altruism are different.

Figure 3.6. Age and Altruism

Figure 3.6 shows the differences between the altruistic behavior of the age groups. Altruistic behavior among respondents in their early adulthood phase are higher compared to adolescents and middle adults. Statistically, the age groups no significance with an effect size of 0.032586.

Figure 3.7. Sex and Altruism

Males have a higher altruistic behavior according to the results yielded by the researchers contradicting past literature that were cited by the researchers earlier. However, this has an effect size of 0.014147 which means that there is no significant difference between the two sexes.

Figure 3.8. Employment status and Altruism

Furthermore, self-employed respondents tend to have a higher donor behavior compared to other groups of employment. It is noted by the researchers that the effect size of these groups is 0.046014 which means that there is no significant difference between the tested groups.

Figure 3.9. Socioeconomic status and altruism

The socioeconomic status among the respondents was divided into seven classes, all with a corresponding monthly income. It was found that respondents who belonged to class E – with a monthly income of PHP 15,780 – PHP 31, 560 – have a higher altruistic behavior compared to those in other groups. Statistically, this group has yielded an effect size of 0.051208 which means that there is no significant differences between the groups.

Figure 3.10. Source and Altruism

In comparison to other sources, it was found that the respondents who have a combination of information sources when donating have higher altruistic behavior compared to other source groups. However, it is shown in figure 3.9 that there are almost no differences between the groups with an effect size of 0.036536.

DISCUSSION

This study aims to explain factors underlying donor behavior particularly demographics, altruism, and empathy among Filipino donor-participants who have been donating during the pandemic. After analyzing data from 348 respondents, the researchers have answered the questions that were formulated during the study.

Past literature argued that women are more likely to showcase altruism compared to men (Andreoni et al., 2015) however, there were more male donor-respondents compared to females in the National Capital Region, Philippines. Most of these donor-respondents come from the adolescent group (ages 18-22 years old), are students, and are earning less than PHP 7, 890.00 confirming past literature that have argued that younger participants with lower income tend to participate more in donation activities.

In terms of age, individuals who belong to the early adulthood (23-39 years old) classification was found to have higher donor behavior compared to other groups, contradicting past literature that states that younger individuals have higher donation behavior. Males also have a higher donation behavior compared to females in contrast to Van Rijn and colleagues' (2019) study where they have found that females have higher tendencies in donating. Self-employed individuals were also found to be donating more compared to private employed, students, and government employed donors. Individuals who are also earning PHP 78,900-PHP 118,350 per month was also found to be donating more compared to other classes with higher and lower income. Donor-respondents who get their information from newspapers have a higher donation intention compared to those who utilize other sources such as social media, television, and peers. However, it was found that the presented independent variables of demographics, source, empathy, and altruism are not significant predictors of donor behavior in the Philippines, specifically in the National Capital Region. After analyzing the variables using ANOVA and regression, it was found that these variables are not predictor of donor behavior in contrast to past literature in other contexts.

In the analysis of the differences between the variables when grouped according to demographics and source, the results yielded no significant difference. Past literature have argued that in prediction of donor behavior, the presented variables of demographics, source, empathy, and altruism are significant predictors, however in this study these variables are not and that these may depend on the context of where the donation behavior is intended. Empathy and altruism may be present in these individuals, but the researchers considered that these individuals might have gone through the same situations as the receivers of donation during the peak of the pandemic.

Conclusions

The researchers have found that demographics such as age, sex, and income impact the likeliness of donor behavior in an individual. Contrary to past literature or studies of van Esch et al., (2021), (Verhaert & Van den Poel, 2011), and (Y. K. Lee & Chang, 2007), empathy was found to be a non-predictor of donor behavior among Filipino donors. Same with empathy, altruism as an independent variable shows that it does not predict or has no significant relationship towards donor behavior, which are opposed to

the past studies made by Green & Schneider, (2018), Andreoni et al., (2015), and Grueter et al., (2016). These two independent variables (empathy and altruism) are not evident towards donor behavior within the context of Philippines. External environmental factors were also found to have no impact on the donor behavior of donors.

The researchers conclude that, although the results of their study showed that altruism and empathy has no significant relationship towards donor behavior, this study still confirms that the theory of warm glow (which has argued that an individual feels a higher level of satisfaction or feels a sense of joy whenever they get to do actions that are altruistic in nature, in the context of this study, donations) is still present since there are still people who gives with an altruistic behavior. However the researchers note that the existing altruistic and empathic behavior among donor-respondents are different from those of the Western context and the motivational factors of donation behavior can not solely be based from the variables presented in the literature due to cultural differences. Surprisingly, there are still altruistic individuals despite the difficulty of surviving during the crisis since it was confirmed people still want to help other individuals who are under the poverty line (e.g. doing community pantries). Past literature has discussed that altruistic behavior will go hand in hand with empathy, however based on the results, this was not the case in the context of Filipinos.

The researchers also conclude, although still open for discussion and further research, that the low relationship between empathy and donor behavior may have stemmed from the fact that all individuals have gone through the same hardships during the course of the pandemic. With these results, it is safe to say that this theory of Warm Glow is still present, but not within the Philippine context, as well within the COVID-19 pandemic.

Recommendations

Through these results, researchers would be able to know how different factors have affected the donation behavior of Filipinos under circumstances such as the pandemic and how a crisis affects both their altruism and empathy. This would also help future researchers of the same field to accurately determine the factors that may impact the altruistic and empathic behavior of Filipino individuals.

The researchers would also like to note that the participants in this study, specifically the type of donation that the donor-participants did were only limited to charitable donors who donate using money or in-kind donations. The researchers recommend those with the same interest of study to explore the other types of donors which can include blood donors, organ donors, and such.

The data in this study were gathered via online platforms including Facebook and emails. The researchers recommend that future researchers who would like to expand or elaborate this study to gather data via face-to-face sessions. The researchers would also recommend exploring genders as this study was limited to males and females.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers dealt with individuals who have experiences in donating in different charitable organizations and strict procedures were observed during the collection of data. The researchers have provided the participants with informed consent stating their participation is fully voluntary and that they are given the option to stop answering the interview questions when they would feel uncomfortable, or they feel like stopping at any moment. The participants were also ensured that they would remain anonymous and all answers that were provided were strictly confidential. The data provided by the participants are used strictly for this research.

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